

Beyond a Quarter Century: A Civil Society Critique of South Africa's Access to Information Law and the Path to Reform

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Twenty-five years later, South Africa, the first African country to acknowledge that access to information is imperative for development and was later passed into law through the Promotion of Access to Information Act (PAIA). The main objective of the law was to allow ordinary citizens to request and access information from the government and hold it accountable using a transparency framework. The study's two-fold approach aims to explore the CSOs' perspectives on the promotion of PAIA and assess if there is a need for legislative reforms to enhance its efficiency. Against this background, the study used a qualitative research approach to collect primary data through semi-structured interviews. The data were thematically analysed using ATLAS.ti and content analysis, which revealed that PAIA has promoted a culture of openness, countering the secrecy culture that was the norm during apartheid. The findings further reflected that an improved execution, supported by training and public awareness, could improve information access without any need for legislative changes. The study's conclusions revealed a serious challenge of public awareness regarding PAIA, necessitating the need for severe penalties to deter officials from obstructing access, as supported by the South African Information Regulator office. The study contributes by highlighting the current policy discourse and advocating for a comprehensive implementation and reform of the PAIA legislation to align with the latest developments in the South African context. Further contributions are to aggravate debate on the issue and improve the PAIA's effectiveness on the promotion of access to information and transparency and accountability due to reforms.

Keywords: Promotion of access to information act, freedom of information, civil society organisations

Before the democratic dispensation in 1994, South Africa was predominantly ruled under a culture of secrecy during apartheid. Section 32 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) introduced the Promotion of Access to Information Act (PAIA), a legislative document, enforced into law in March 2001. The PAIA was celebrated widely as a unique law due to its coverage of information from both public and private bodies, which other Freedom of Information (FOI) laws across the globe could not do. Despite being celebrated as the foundation of democratic transparency and accountability in South Africa, scholarly evidence proves that there is still a need to explore its effectiveness, specifically from the civil society and communities' viewpoint. According to Knežević and Reljanović (2022), Okoli (2024), Dick (2005), and Mojapelo (2024), many countries still encounter implementation challenges in access to information.

The concept of access to information, or the PAIA in the South African context, has been extensively studied. Some of the scholars

who explored the concept are not limited to Calland (2009), Darch and Underwood (2005), Osawe (2022), Legodi and Mukonza (2024), and McKinley (2021). Both in South Africa and elsewhere around the world, countries still grapple with the challenges of implementing access to information laws (Calland, 2002). South Africa's legal framework for ensuring transparent access to information is considered one of the most progressive in the world. However, its processes for providing access to information are still faced with serious inefficiencies.

The study aims to achieve two objectives: examining the views and experiences of civil society organisations on the implementation of the Promotion of Access to Information Act, and determining whether legislative reforms, through an evaluation of the legislation's limitations, are necessary. A qualitative research approach has been used to meet the article's objectives of determining whether the legislation's shortfalls warrant an amendment or not.

South Africa remains one of the most unequal countries in the world. The current levels of inequality are the legacy of the segregation and marginalisation of most of its citizenry in every aspect of South Africa's socio-economic development before, during, and after apartheid (Leibbrandt & Pabón, 2021). According to Stats SA (2023), the percentage of households with access to the internet through all means increased from 28,0% in 2010 to 78,6% in 2023. It further asserts that the Internet is a vital resource for accessing information and communicating with others. However, nationally, only 3,8% of households did not have access to either landlines or cellular phones. In comparison, only 0,1% of South African households exclusively used landlines (Stats SA, 2023). These are the disparities caused by the legacy of segregation during apartheid, which are carried over to the democratic dispensation, and

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need to be addressed as part of curbing access to information-related challenges. According to Stats SA (2023), communication plays an important role in the fundamental operation of a society, as it links people and businesses, facilitating communication and the flow of ideas and information, and coordinating economic activities and development.

In well-functioning democracies, there is a presence of civil society that holds the government accountable. In most countries, civil society organisations (CSOs) form an integral part of democratic governance. According to Mlambo, Zubane, and Mlambo (2020), civil society organisations promote good governance through transparency, uphold the rule of law, human rights and combat corruption. They further argue that CSOs act as watchdogs by holding the government accountable and assessing if the government serves the public.

Similarly, Anyalebechi, Amabibi, Hart, and Eyina (2023) acknowledge that civil society is a key agent in promoting democracy. Civil society organisations can bridge the gap between grassroots realities and policy, protect human rights and efficiently deliver services to the public. The South African civil society plays a significant role in fostering relationships with the government, which often enhances its capacity (Gumede, 2016). These proclamations emphasise the significance of state and civil society relationships for good governance.

To address the legacy of secrecy, misinformation and selective dissemination of information, a relook at the legislation is recommended, so that it informs possible reforms or not. During the process, acknowledging all relevant actors, including civil society organisations, as critical stakeholders is encouraged. Hence, the article's objective to explore the experiences and insights of CSOs personnel who perform their advocacy work using the PAIA as a mechanism to access information from the government. This study incites current policy debate on the PAIA legislation reform in South Africa, which will then support democracy, public participation and good governance.

Review of Literature

Ngoepe and Mojapelo (2023) assert that Freedom of Information (FOI) laws are indispensable, especially for the realisation of an all-inclusive democracy. The world's first FOI law, the Freedom of the Press Act, was approved in 1766 by Sweden (Banisar, 2002). According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), Article 19 states that:

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes the freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive, and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.

Figure 1

Data of Countries with ATI Legislation (Global Investigative Journalism Network, 2025)

The declaration paved the way for the adoption of more human

rights treaties at the global and regional levels. Finland enacted its law in 1951, while the United States passed its Freedom of Information Act in 1966. France followed suit in 1978, and Canada, Australia, and New Zealand did so in 1982 (Banisar, 2002). According to Mabillard (2016), the FOI laws have doubled between 1996 and 2001 and tripled between 2004 and 2014. The graph shows the evolution of the number of FOI laws (or equivalent) since 1950.

Currently, the top three countries with the highest scores on access to information (ATI) ratings include Afghanistan, Mexico, and Serbia. According to Freedom.org (n.d.), the amendments to Mexico's freedom of information law have made it the best country with access to information law in the world. However, the Centre for Law and Democracy (CLD) claims Afghanistan has toppled both Serbia and Mexico, as it now scored 139 points out of 150, compared to Mexico's 136 points and Serbia's 135 points. Comparing South Africa with Afghanistan and Mexico on ATI legislation gives clear evidence of the shortcomings of PAIA in terms of what could be done to reform the legislation and improve its efficiency (de Villiers, 2024). For example, Section 18 of PAIA states that:

A request for access must be made in the prescribed form to the information officer of the public body concerned at his or her address or fax number, or electronic mail address (PAIA, 2000, s.18).

Whereas, according to international standards, it simply means there are clear and relatively simple procedures for making requests. Requests may be submitted by any means of communication, with no requirement to use official forms or to state that the information is being requested under the Access to Information Law (Centre for Law & Democracy, 2025). However, according to PAIA, an information request must be made using the prescribed form. The second example is in Section 74 of PAIA, which states that:

(1) A requester may lodge an internal appeal against a decision of the information officer of a public body referred to in paragraph (a) of the definition of "public body" in section 1- (a) to refuse an access request; or (b) taken in terms of section 22, 26(1) or 29(3), in relation to that requester with the relevant authority...The appeal fee payable in respect of the lodging of an internal appeal by a requester against the refusal of his or her request for access, as contemplated in section 75(3) (a) of the Act, is R 50.00 (PAIA, 2000, s.74-75).

The law offers an internal appeal process which is simple, free of charge, and should be completed within clear timelines, that is, 20 working days or less. However, the PAIA offers an internal appeal process, but it is not free. These are some of the PAIA inclusions that might be obstructive to the implementation of the legislation (PAIA, 2000, s.75).

Just like in many countries around the world, access to information in South Africa is a fundamental human right enshrined in the Constitution (1996) and subsequently in freedom of information (FOI) legislation - the Promotion of Access to Information Act (PAIA) of 2000 (Ngoepe & Mojapelo, 2023; Nkwe & Ngoepe, 2021; Birkinshaw, 2006; SAHA, 2019; & Mathiesen, 2008). In 2024, South Africa marked a significant turning point in its history, thirty years since the emergence of democracy. The milestone represents the ongoing quest for justice, equality, and freedom for all its citizens, in addition to marking the passage of time. One of the milestones recorded was the passing of the legislation on access to information, which counteracted one of the

main characteristics of the apartheid regime, the state's obsession with official secrecy, which, according to Arko-Cobbah (2008), was virtually a way of life.

Despite the milestone of the adoption of the PAIA in South Africa, literature has attested that there are challenges with the implementation of the legislation. According to Nkwe and Ngoepe (2021), there are still gaps relating to its implementation, and records management is cited as one of the contributors (Mojapelo, 2025; Mutula & Wamukoya, 2009). The recognition of the right of access to information during the transition to democracy was a central pillar of South Africa's democracy, as information became a crucial resource for the liberation forces (Arko-Cobbah, 2008).

Civil society groups have played a key role in the framing and adoption of information laws in many countries, including South Africa (Banisar, 2002; Dimba & Calland, 2003). In South Africa, civil society's role in governance emerged through liberation movements such as the African National Congress (ANC), United

Democratic Front (UDF) and workers' unions among townships' civic associations between the early 1980s and 1990s (Glaser, 1997; Bratton, 1994; Lehman, 2008; & Swilling, 1990). These formations formed part of a strong and early civil society that ended the South African apartheid era. The civil society ecosystem has since subsided due to several reasons, including reduced funding and diminished eagerness to fight, hence the collapse of the apartheid regime. Despite the current weakness of the civil society ecosystem, it remains a critical part of democratic governance.

The Promotion of access to Information Act and Democratic Accountability

According to Arko-Cobbah (2008), as a precondition for a democratic state, the PAIA is meant to establish the right of access to information to pursue values of accountability, openness, transparency, rule of law, and participation. As it is illustrated in the table below, a summary of provisions of Section 32 of the Constitution is provided (South African Constitution, 2006).

Table 1
Summary of Key Provisions of PAIA

Aspect	Summary	Shortcomings
Purpose	To offer the right of access to information through openness, transparency and accountability.	It does not elaborate on how illiterate and people with disabilities are covered, making its provision vague.
Scope	The legislation affects both public and private bodies in South Africa.	Exceptionally expansive compared to FOI laws globally, but implementation remains uneven.
Right of Access	Individual requesters are allowed to access information from both public and private bodies in South Africa, with certain exceptions.	Falls short on clarity on accessible formats and language considerations in a multilingual society.
Request Process	Only standardised forms are used to request information, with time limits attached for a timely response from those bodies.	Procedural requirements may be difficult and limit access for marginalised groups.
Exceptions	In cases of privacy violations, the bridge of security, access to information, might be denied.	Exceptions are often broadly interpreted, leading to refusals.
Appeals and Review	Internal appeals processes and reviews by requesters are allowed through the Information Regulator's office.	Appeal processes can be slow and resource-intensive for requesters.
Enforcement	Oversight vested in the South African Information Regulator with powers to monitor compliance and impose penalties.	Weak enforcement and compliance challenges continue to undermine effectiveness.

Note. Source: Authors' illustration

Democracy, which means "rule by the people," was coined from the Greek word *dimokratia* (Ezetah, 1996). The concept, according to Ezetah, is understood better through the theory of civil government by John Locke, which is founded on the initial presupposition of equality for all people. Apparently, South Africa is a constitutional democracy, as McKinley (2021) opposes the assertion that the so-called "people's democracy" is not democratic. He argues that there are worrying signs of retreat from grounded, people's democracy, of an 'undemocratic' democracy gaining the upper hand. He cites issues such as increased control of information, disguised contempt for democratic oversight and unequal application of the law, and securitisation of the state as some of his observations.

Jones and Stokke (2005) address those who advocate for participatory democracy, stating that the term is empty if it co-exists comfortably with unequal access to resources and opportunities, and

if popular participation in politics is limited to periodic voting for a decision-making elite. Machin and Ruser (2023) similarly, agree that the 'grassroots' participation encouraged by civil society organisations and social movements can be seen as a source of democracy.

According to Ngoepe and Mojapelo (2023), the maturity level of democracy can be measured by the extent to which the right to access information is protected by legislation, such as the FOI legislation (i.e., PAIA in the South African context), and how well it is implemented. Democracy is dependent on a well-informed citizenry with equal access to justice and the ability to decisively deal with a government that undermines the will of the people (Neuman, 2002). In the South African context, McKinley (2021) argues that a significant component of the struggle against apartheid was fundamentally a struggle for the democratic reclamation of human

rights. McKinley adds that those rights included the right to know, at the heart of which is access to information to ensure democratic transparency and to hold all power to account.

Implementation Challenges in South Africa

Since it was passed into law in 2001, the PAIA has faced several challenges in implementation. Despite its elevation and being celebrated as the cornerstone of democratic governance in the country, it has never achieved its optimal human rights goal of providing access to information to all people, irrespective of their literacy levels and disability statuses. Banisar (2002) argues that the availability of legislation on access to information does not translate into automatic availability of information. Banisar points out that this is due to weak enforcement mechanisms. Mojapelo (2025) agrees with Banisar's assertion that the legislation in both South Africa and Zimbabwe is vague and needs revision to enhance effective implementation.

Similarly, Allan (2009) acknowledges that the PAIA legislation has shortfalls, especially on exemptions and the power to hold non-compliant accountable. In his study, Mojapelo (2024) asserts that the participants in his study agreed that the Information Regulator South Africa (IRSA) exists to provide oversight and monitoring, but its powers are limited, as one area of concern. Whereas Arko-Cobbah (2008) argues that for the Act to succeed, a good information management system needs to be put in place. Arko-Cobbah further raises an interesting concept of the role of libraries, especially the advocacy role of the Library and Information Association of South Africa (LIASA) on the improvement of records management. Sound management of information contained in records and other information systems of public and private bodies is the sine qua non of democratic governance, as it enhances service delivery, promotes efficiency and integrity in government (Mutula & Wamukoya, 2009; Manek & Mosweu, 2022).

Furthermore, Ngoepe and Mojapelo (2023) argue that all public records belong to the public, as the name suggests, so why pay a price for something that belongs to you? The assertion is supported by Arko-Cobbah (2008) that affordability, public awareness of civil and human rights, levels of information literacy, the coherence of national political discourse, and the perceived chance of success are some of the hindrances.

The literature points to the recording and management of information, requesting processes, exemption of certain records, information literacy and low public awareness, lack of organisational capacity and resources, culture of secrecy, digital divide and lack of a culture of openness and transparency as some of the barriers for access to information (Darch & Underwood, 2005; SAHA, 2019; Nkwe & Ngoepe, 2021; Arthur, 2021; McKinley, 2014; & Malinga, 2025). The literature demonstrates that access to information in South Africa is still constrained by several factors that hinder its implementation. Further, highlighting the non-existence of effective enforcement apparatuses, whereby the authorities or agencies responsible for the legislation's comprehensive implementation are lacking, which exacerbates the challenges associated with the legislation's efficiency (de Villiers, 2024; Ebrahim, 2010; & Allan & Currie, 2007).

For example, according to a recent report by Sunday World Newspaper, the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF) is calling for the scrapping of mandatory expiry policies on unused prepaid data and airtime in South Africa, arguing that the practice is exploitative and

unconstitutional (Mdakane, 2025). According to Mdakane (2025), the EFF claims that such expiry rules, which are often justified by the mobile operators as industry norms, restrict South African citizens' access to information and widen the digital divide, because losing the unused data further undermines the ability of marginalised poor to access job opportunities, education, and ordinary service delivery. It further argues that it is organisations like the Independent Communications Authority of South Africa (ICASA) that perpetuate the situation by not addressing the issue of the expiry date of unused prepaid data.

Civil Society Engagement with the PAIA

Civil society is an extensive and flexible concept encompassing a wide range of organisations and actors, i.e., those operating independently from the state and market forces. Weisskircher (2020) posits that the concept has its historical roots in political philosophy. He acknowledges that it was Aristotle who introduced the concept of *politike koinonia*, or the so-called political community, and later in Latin as *societas civilis*. One of the earlier scholars who described what civil society is, Alexis de Tocqueville, asserts that it serves as a vital component of democracy that limits central power and encourages civic participation (Weisskircher, 2020).

According to Longley (2022), civil society remains hard to define, deeply complex, and resistant to being specifically categorised or interpreted. The assertion is supported by Tjahja, Meyer, and Shahin (2021) that it is a highly contested concept. The scholars further posit that civil society is seen as specifically serving the purpose of remedying the democratic deficits in global governance. In their study, Tjahja, Meyer, and Shahin (2021) define civil society as non-governmental, non-commercial actors who participate in governance processes, including NGOs, academic institutions, individual researchers, technical experts, and advocacy groups.

Henriques (2007) defines civil society as the network of institutions of private origin and a public purpose in which communities share goods, meanings, and values, significantly contributing to the progress or decline of governance. According to Clayton, Oakley, and Taylor (2000), the network of institutions may include religious groups, workers' unions, professional bodies, sports and arts groups, and traditional and/or informal organisations. Paudyal (2023) notes that these definitions highlight the different aspects of civil society, such as its voluntary nature, its autonomy, and its role in the public sphere in promoting good governance, human rights, and social justice.

To spearhead a meaningful engagement with the state on behalf of communities to realise socio-economic rights (Arko-Cobbah & Olivier, 2016) argue that CSOs use litigation and advocacy work to achieve their goals. Dick (2005) agrees that civil society organisations, through South Africa's constitutional right of access to information, have been committed to making the PAIA work. For example, the Treatment Action Campaign (TAC) litigated the government for failing to provide Nevirapine, an antiretroviral drug for pregnant women.

In South Africa today, there is almost no party of opposition that omits mention of the importance of civil society (Fine, 1992). Most scholars on civil society agree, however, that civil society has an institutional core constituted by voluntary associations outside the sphere of the state and the economy (Flyvbjerg, 1998). The variety in definitions reflects the complex nature of the concept and sometimes contradictory roles of civil society.

For this study, a basic understanding of what civil society represents is crucial, as the aim is not to conceptualise the concept. However, it is to familiarise readers with the concept of civil society and its relation to the study's objective. The assertion is supported by Sombatpoonsiri (2023) that civil society is dynamic, reflecting a broader power struggle in society. He further submits that other scholars, such as Callahan (1999) and Lee Hock Guan (2004), argue that instead of fixing our gaze on what defines civil society, we should pay more attention to civil society as a site of conflict and power contestation.

To understand the association between civil society and PAIA, Calland (2000) poses a question: would South Africa have ended up with a Promotion to Access to Information Act legislation or a weaker version of the legislation had there not been the civil society coalition pushing for a strong piece of enabling legislation? Calland argues that a civil society lobby group such as the Open Democracy Campaign Group (ODAC), human rights, democracy, and environmental organisations, together with trade unions, are the ones that advocated for a stronger piece of legislation to give effect to the constitutional right of access to information as required by section 32 of the Constitution of South Africa (1996).

To further understand the theoretical lens that guided the study, a utilitarianism theory was adopted, as it recognises the exclusion of the voices of the marginalised from access to information rights. Utilitarianism is held to be the view that the morally right action is the action that produces what is called the "most good" (Driver, 2022). Furthermore, Driver (2022) asserts that the theory is a form of consequentialism: the right action is understood entirely in terms of consequences produced, simply meaning to bring about 'the greatest amount of good for the greatest number'.

Jeremy Bentham developed the theory, and it emphasises the idea that laws and policies should aim at producing the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people (Bentham, 1950). The purpose of legislation, according to Bentham, is primarily to promote the contentment and well-being of the people and to maximise pleasure and minimize pain (which is the core principle of Bentham's utilitarian philosophy). The Promotion of Access to Information Act (PAIA) was introduced as a tool to promote transparency, accountability, and good governance, all aimed at increasing the "most good" as Bentham would call it (happiness, well-being, empowerment) for the greatest number (citizens, civil society, media, etc.). So, with weak implementation or bureaucratic processes, the likelihood of attaining the "most good" for the benefit of all society is extremely limited.

According to the SAHA (2018), there is no legal obligation under the PAIA that mandates CSOs to conduct awareness and educational initiatives. However, SAHA, through its extensive Freedom of Information Programme, conducted community trainings to raise public awareness and education about the legislation. Civic society groups have an enormous role to play in poverty alleviation projects. Their importance is to unite people when battling poverty to engage in strategic plans and diverse government programmes (Ngumbela, 2023). Prior research has found that CSOs have played a critical role in providing necessary supplies and resources when citizens were subjected to strict restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Levine et al., Heller, 2023).

Calls for Legislative Reforms

Law reform, according to Rustin (2021), is one of the strategies used

by liberal democracies to guarantee the inclusion of people who were previously denied citizenship rights. The law is a short term for an overly complex aggregation of principles, norms, ideas, rules, practices, and the activities of agencies of legislation, administration, adjudication, and enforcement, backed by political power and legitimacy (Moore, 1973).

According to Mendel (2011), the issue of amending the legal framework for the right to information is a topical and important one, even though it has not received much attention in the literature. Mendel argues that amendments could be better described simply as attempts to modernize access regimes to consider developments that have occurred since the law was first passed, for example, due to technological developments or changes in implementation mechanisms that foster efficiency of the legislation. Allan (2009) adds that amendments can either take place due to challenges associated with exceptions. For example, the PAIA's confidentiality exemption has been inappropriately used in a blanket fashion to prevent access to records without giving due consideration to their substantive content. The other reasons cited by Allan (2009) are ineffective appeal mechanisms, weak enforcement powers, and other legislation contradicting the PAIA.

Having witnessed a peaceful transition in 1994 whereby equality was guaranteed through the passing of the Constitution of 1996 and the Bill of Rights, a cornerstone of democracy in South Africa, enshrines the rights of all people and affirms the democratic values of human dignity, equality, and freedom (Constitution, 1996). Section 32 of the Constitution guarantees the right to access to information. According to Moore (1973), legislation is often passed to alter the existing social arrangements in specified ways. Legislation can directly impact its citizens and is thus a key instrument in bringing about change in their lives (Rustin, 2021).

According to Mojapelo (2025), the enactment of the PAIA in South Africa proved the commitment by the government to the promotion of democracy and public participation. However, since the passing of the PAIA in 2001, much has not changed. The enactment has not automatically translated into democratic and public participation of all ordinary citizens in the country (McKinley, 2021; de Waal, Jakins, Klarmann, Green, & D'Cruze, 2022; & Mojapelo, 2025). The legislation's potential to enhance democracy in the country is limited, hence the need for reform (McKinley, 2021). According to Mojapelo (2023), the current implementation and oversight role of the PAIA falls solely on the Information Regulator (IR), as the function was previously bestowed to the SAHRC.

In her article *Information Regulator readies for AI era*, Malinga (2025) posits that the Information Regulator's office has acknowledged that there is a need for legislation reforms:

"We've talked about law reform, and we've had some experience with these laws and some of the things we have to do. We are starting to see where the gaps are, and law reform is something that is going to be front and centre for us."

The acknowledgment by the Information Regulator is in support of Ngoepe and McKinley's assertions on the need for reforms of the legislation (Viljoen, 2024). The reform suggestions come on the heels of other previous amendments, which did not bear much fruit. Listed in the table below are the amendments that took place since the Act was enacted in 2001 (Ebrahim, 2010; van der Berg, 2017; & de Villiers, 2024).

Table 2*PAIA Amendments Timeline*

Date	Event
2 February 2000	PAIA (Promotion of Access to Information Act, Act No. 2 of 2000) is assented to by the President.
9 March 2001	PAIA comes into force (commencement date) in many of its provisions.
2001-2003	Several early amendments via other Acts (e.g., Judicial Matters Amendment Act, Financial Intelligence Centre Act, etc.) adjusted PAIA.
2013	Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) enacted (Assent: 19 November 2013) - includes provision for establishing the Information Regulator.
1 July 2020	POPIA commences; a one-year grace period begins for entities to align with its requirements.
PAI Amendment Act, 2019	Amended PAIA; key among changes was the requirement for private funding disclosure of political parties and related matters. Act assented in May 2020. Takes effect 1 April 2021.
30 June 2021	The Information Regulator assumes responsibility for PAIA regulatory functions from the South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC).
1 July 2021	POPIA becomes fully operational; The PAIA amendments under the 2019 Amendment Act are in force. All public and private bodies are required to have PAIA manuals (ending previous exemptions).
27 August 2021	PAIA Regulations are published under the new regime of the Information Regulator.

Note. Source: Authors' illustration

In 2002, the first amendment to the Act, the PAIA Amendment Act, 2002 (Act No. 54 of 2002), was introduced. This amendment was necessitated by the need to clarify certain definitions and procedures, as well as to extend time limits for compliance by private bodies. The technical changes and refinements to improve the implementation processes of PAIA were made in response to calls for review and reform by civil society from 2009 to 2013. The main course of contention was about practical barriers such as administrative delays and a lack of compliance by both public and private bodies in reporting on PAIA.

In 2015, we further saw the introduction of the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) being passed. The POPI Act, even though not a direct amendment to the PAIA, it however somehow overlaps with the PAIA concerning personal information and personal data access. That brought about a need to discuss how the two legislations interact with each other, due to issues of the right to access versus the right to privacy. The inherent contradiction between openness and secrecy may be seen as straightforward: where the realisation of one goal (openness) tends to suspend the realisation of the other goal (secrecy), and vice versa (Klaaren, 2024).

The 2018 Constitutional ruling in *My Vote Counts NPC vs The Minister of Justice and Correctional Services* brought a forced amendment, resulting in the PAIA Amendment Act (Act No. 31 of 2019). In this case, the Court found that PAIA was inadequate in enabling access to information about private funding of political parties and independent candidates (Cachalia, 2017). The process brought a new Political Party Funding Act 6 of 2018, which is a separate law, but supplements PAIA on issues of access to information on political party funding (Porat, 2021).

According to Moore (1973), the relationship between law and social change has been the subject of vast scholarly debate, with a compromise emerging around their interdependent nature. Moore argues that law should be viewed as a semi-autonomous social field, defined not by territorial boundaries but by its ability to produce and sustain rules, customs, and symbols that hold significance for a given

community. He argues that social change, characterised by reforms and transformations within societal institutions and practices, is frequently driven by shifts in political, economic, and cultural beliefs. With changing times and observations on the overwhelming evidence suggesting poor implementation of the legislation, the legislation on access to information warrants legislative reforms.

Method

The study employed a qualitative exploratory research design, which was best suited for exploring the experiences and perceptions of CSOs regarding the PAIA. The study measured the CSOs' perceptions and lived experiences of access to information using semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis. Qualitative research offers the truth value often obtained through the discovery of human experiences as lived and perceived by participants (Krefting, 1991).

The primary data collection was conducted through semi-structured one-on-one online interviews through Microsoft Teams with key participants from the five selected CSOs. The study acknowledges certain limitations, such as the sample size, which does not fully reflect the heterogeneity of the South African civil society ecosystem. Most CSOs have fewer personnel working on PAIA-related projects. That forced the sample selection to be skewed toward CSOs with established access to information engagements only.

The selection of participants was done in a way to ensure a representation of civil society organisations that had a diverse engagement with the PAIA on access and deployment of information for development, governance purposes, and holding the government accountable. The ten participants were purposively sampled across a diverse CSOs ecosystem that specifically uses PAIA for their advocacy work. According to Kumar (2011), sampling is a process of selecting a few from a bigger group (the population), and purposive sampling is used to select respondents who are most likely to yield appropriate and useful information (Kelly, Bourgeault, & Dingwall, 2010). The participants were former and current

employees sampled from the CSOs that used PAIA in their advocacy work for a couple of years. To protect the identity of the participants, numbers (e.g., P3, P1 or P5) were used as pseudonyms for research ethical reasons.

Supplementary data were drawn from secondary sources such as books, e-books, peer-reviewed journal articles, and annual government reports on legislative matters on PAIA. The study used semi-structured interviews to collect primary data using an interview schedule developed through the guidance of previously reviewed literature. Due to the qualitative nature or design of the study, inferential statistical analysis was not contemplated; however, the data were analysed thematically to contextualise the sampled participants' demographics.

A thematic data analysis was adopted to identify emerging themes and categories (see Table 3) below as an illustration. A theme refers

to a specific pattern of meaning found in the data (Joffe, 2012). Whereas thematic data analysis, according to Braun and Clarke (2006), is defined as a method for identifying and analysing patterns of meaning in a data set.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings from interviews with the ten participants drawn from the CSOs engaged in advocacy work that utilises the PAIA. The participants, all university-educated and occupying middle-management positions, had between six and ten years of professional experience. Data were analysed inductively using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis approach, from which the codes, themes, and illustrative excerpts were derived as illustrated in Table 3 below.

Table 3
Summary of Codes, Themes, and Excerpts from the Data

Codes	Themes	Excerpts
Lack of Enforcement	Implementation vs Amendment	"The legislation is sound as it is; however, training needs to be given on it." (P6)
Training for Officials	Implementation vs Amendment	"Information officers need to be educated and get some training on how to deal with PAIA." (P5)
Public Education	Education and Public Awareness	"The general public doesn't know how PAIA is used." (P4)
Bureaucracy	Administration and Access issues	"We need access to information and not access to mere records." (P10)
Digital Age Limitations	Need for Amendment	"It was drafted in a pre-digital age and so it's not fit for purpose." (P9)
Non-compliance Penalties	Enforcement and Accountability	"Maybe we should look at a kind of penalty when you are not complying." (P8)

Note. Source: Authors' illustration

Generally, the participants understood the undertaking of PAIA and its constitutional obligations. In the same breath, several participants showed some concern about its implementation, arguing that, practically, the law does not benefit or serve the marginally located citizens. The key finding, which seemed to be central, was 'accessibility'. Participants highlighted over-reliance on formal dissemination channels, which often marginalise and exclude most of the population. They suggested proactive disclosure and dissemination of information through multiple channels to mitigate the challenges.

There were opposing views on reforming the legislation versus the Act's implementation. Some participants were for the amendment due to ever-changing technological innovations, whereas others argued against reform and pushed for pure enhancement of implementation mechanisms. They suggested introducing binding penalties, especially for those who deliberately ignore compliance with the Act. Those in disagreement with legislative reforms argued that improved institutional capacity, training of information officers, and awareness campaigns can strengthen the efficiency of the law, as they do not believe that amendments alone can resolve the systemic challenges.

Generally, the findings displayed opposing viewpoints on PAIA's effectiveness. Using thematic analysis, the findings highlighted

several interrelated themes, namely: bureaucratic and accessibility issues, the need for amendments, implementation versus amendment, public awareness and education, and enforcement and accountability, which are expanded further below.

Bureaucratic and Accessibility Issues

The findings suggest that the PAIA processes to access information from the government are not user-friendly. They are too bureaucratic or administrative, making access to information for ordinary citizens problematic. The participants envisage a simplified process without paperwork, as they complain about the rigorous process of downloading forms that require careful completion before the requester can obtain the desired information, which might be a deterrent.

According to the Centre for Law and Democracy, the PAIA requires that requests be made using the prescribed form, as they believe that requests may be submitted by any means of communication, with no requirement to use official forms or to state that the information is being requested under the access to information law. The finding suggests that there are laborious processes that need to be followed to access the information. In sureness, the process for obtaining information through the PAIA is frequently time-consuming and bureaucratic, often resulting in an

'information management crisis', despite the legal framework (Legodi & Mukonza, 2024; & Desrochers, 2024).

Need for Amendments

30% of participants supported amending PAIA. The participants (P7, P9, & P10) believe that the PAIA should be amended to account for digital record-keeping and reflect technological developments and meet modern governance requirements. Participant (P9) alludes that "It needs an update anyway, irrespective of whether it was sort of working or not." The finding was supported by van der Berg's assertion (2017) that 'using the Information Regulator's authority to suggest the PAIA amendment, including record-generating obligations and addressing the so-called over-exacting standards of the public interest override'.

Implementation vs. Amendment

40% of the participants believe that the problem is not with PAIA itself but with its implementation. Participants (P2, P4, P5, & P6) argue that better implementation, training, and awareness would improve access to information without the need for amendments. For example, Participant (P6) asserts that "Training on how to interpret PAIA applications should be made compulsory for state entities." This is a recurring theme among the participants. The CLD's findings are that PAIA's section 83(3) stipulates that the Information Regulator may train information officers and deputy information officers of public bodies. It may train, but is not required to, whereas countries like Mexico are making it compulsory to train information officers. Mandatory enforcement for training programs should be one of PAIA's priorities. The findings suggest an increased non-compliance with processes. For example, non-response or delayed response by information officers due to institutional capacity (de Waal, Jakins, & Klarmann, 2024).

Public Awareness and Education

The findings suggested that a lack of awareness of the PAIA was a crucial challenge. The participants indicated how fundamental it is to educate both government officials and the public on how to use PAIA to access information and hold the government accountable. This points to the need to introduce educational empowerment programmes on PAIA. This finding is supported by de Villiers' (2024) assertion that it is of paramount importance that the South African government, through information agencies, continues to create public awareness about the right to access information.

Enforcement and Accountability

The two participants (P8 & P10) advocated for consequence management that is strong enough to assist in addressing deliberate non-compliance. They further suggested that the Information Regulator should be empowered to impose sanctions for such offences. The finding agrees with the assertion by Peekhaus (2014) that the creation of the office of Information Regulator as an alternative enforcement body was intended to address the weaknesses of PAIA and reliance on courts to settle reviews and appeals. This is in line with what Viljoen (2024) noted, that even the office of the Information Regulator wrote to Parliament to request an amendment to PAIA to empower it to enforce sanctions in case of non-compliance.

However, other scholars cite broad exemption clauses as the primary cause for weak implementation of PAIA (Ntlama, 2003; &

Ebrahim, 2010). Additionally, the scholars further proclaim that inadequate enforcement mechanisms and limited institutional capacity are the impediments. Since there are contested or opposing findings on the PAIA's effectiveness for reforms or enhancing implementation, the utilitarian lens presents a socially beneficial outcome perspective of 'most good' as the ultimate objective that should be the focus. It is believed that determined implementation gaps are likely to undermine this objective, limiting the Act's overall utility.

Inclusively, the study's findings show opposing recommendations, a call for legislative reform versus demands for improved implementation mechanisms. Despite these opposing stances, a need to uphold the constitutional provision of access to information, whereby transparency and accountability are the foundation of democracy, should prevail.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The evidence presented in the study shows that access to information legislation (PAIA) is imperative for human development. To meet and accomplish what the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) envisions in giving effect to the constitutional right of access to information, the proposed reforms are of critical importance to acknowledge and apply to enhance the implementation of the legislation.

The PAIA legislation clearly falls short of the legal robustness required to provide adequate access to information for all people, irrespective of their background. The study's goal was to establish whether the implementation of the PAIA is producing the greatest possible benefit for the greatest number of people. Based on the findings from the CSOs' participants, the real-life consequences, such as corruption, inadequate service delivery, and poverty, are related to weak access to information. Even though the findings give a balanced response on whether the legislation should be amended or not, read through Bentham's utilitarianism theory of an increased 'good' benefit for the majority could be attained if the solutions below, through the reforms grounded in utilitarian rational, are acknowledged and adopted.

Though shortcomings still characterise the PAIA legislation, some recommendations could be adopted to improve its implementation and effective governance. From the literature and thematic analysis findings, some of the recommendations that could be adopted to enhance the effectiveness of the legislation are as follows:

Strengthen Institutional and Legal Frameworks: by improving monitoring systems, updating the PAIA to consider digital developments, making information officers' training mandatory, and imposing harsher sanctions for non-compliance.

Modernise Access to Information Processes: to guarantee effective information access, streamline the PAIA administrative processes with clear deadlines, executing technology-driven systems, for example, online request portals and digital record-keeping.

Strengthened Collaboration and Community Empowerment: reassuring collaborations between CSOs and the state to address shared information-access related issues while supporting local communities with relevant educational campaigns.

Encourage Public Awareness and Educational Campaigns: by advancing a culture of transparency across all spheres of government and integrating PAIA-related content at schools with awareness campaigns to acquaint people with PAIA.

The difficulties associated with the PAIA's inefficiencies can be addressed through the proposed reforms to enhance implementation and enable the realisation of access to information as a basic human right. The study recommends further research on a broader scale, covering other countries that have adopted FOI laws or exploring the inconsistent legislation in South Africa that impacts access to information, such as the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) and the Promotion of Administrative Justice Act (PAJA).

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